

Climate and Earth System Insights and Advances

Science2Policy Meeting
25th September 2025, Brussels

Project Cluster

ESM2025 is building a new generation of Earth system models fitted to support the development of mitigation and adaptation strategies in line with the commitments of the Paris Agreement.

OptimESM brings together increased model resolution & process realism in Earth system models to deliver long-term climate projections for guidance on regional climate change at different levels of global warming, the risk of abrupt Earth system changes & the regional impacts arising from such events.

TipESM aims to improve our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding tipping points.

ClimTip studies climate tipping points – such as polar ice sheets, ocean currents, and tropical forests, and their impacts on biodiversity, agriculture, and societies. It aims to inform global assessments (IPCC/IPBES), adaptation & mitigation strategies.

RESCUE investigates the Earth system response to climate neutrality scenarios, providing science-based policy-relevant recommendations on the role that CO₂ removal can play in the coming decades.

nextGEMS builds storm- and eddy-resolving Earth System Models to advance science, guide policy, and inform applications to support the sustainable management of our planet.

Introductions

SPEAKERS

Roland Séférian
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Knowledge & Engagement
Co-I ESM2025, OptimESM,
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Joeri Rogelj
Co-I ESM2025

Shuting Yang
PI TipESM

Mariana Rocha
Scientific Communication &
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Co-I ESM2025 & OptimESM

Contribution

Torben Koenigk
PI OptimESM

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Co-I RESCUE,
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Co-PI ClimTIP

1. EU Climate Policy

DG CLIMA

2. General Context

CMIP7, IPCC AR7 & the impact of project research

Roland Séférian

EU projects contribution to IPCC

In support of IPCC reports (& model developments + climate services)

2013
AR5 WGI

2018
SR15

2019
SROCC

2019
SRCCL

2021
AR6 WGI

2028/29
AR7

CMIP7 – Assessment Fast-Track & MIPs

AN EVOLVING EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A more continuous approach with small targeted “Fast Track” experiment sets.

The Assessment Fast-Track will respond to the **needs of IPCC AR7** and other national and international policy assessments.

CMIP infrastructure, standards and tools support ongoing science and assessment activities.

This design reflects **extensive feedback** from the modelling centres and wider user community.

CMIP7 – Science Goals and description paper

During CMIP7 planning process, **four key questions emerged**, which the current generation of Earth System Models could address through **multi-model ensemble simulations**.

(More details in Dunne et al., 2025)

Patterns of Sea Surface Change:
How will tropical ocean temperature patterns co-evolve with those at higher latitudes?

Changing Weather:
How will dangerous weather patterns evolve?

Water-Carbon-Climate Nexus:
How will Earth respond to human efforts to manage the carbon cycle?

Tipping Points:
What are the risks of triggering irreversible changes across possible climate trajectories?

CMIP7 – Timing & phasing with IPCC assessment

CMIP7 – Timing & phasing with IPCC assessment

A lot of work, cross-community activities (including infrastructure) are required to successfully achieve these milestones!

CMIP7 – Development of new future scenarios

A new set of scenarios help to answer key questions

General framing

Paradigm change: from **possible** to **plausible** range of scenarios

- Starting point: status-quo climate policies
- High-Scenario: Roll-back of climate policies modelled with SSP3-type scenario

Model improvements and updates

- Socioeconomic drivers, techno-economics, air pollutants, non-CO₂ greenhouse gases
- New model versions (sectors, CDR, forestry, ...)

Status: Full scenario protocol and scenarios close to final submission

AR7 WGI Structure

- = focus/deep dive
- = core chapters
- = xWG elements

Current status and trends

 Chapter 4
Advances in process understanding of Earth system changes

Futures

 Chapter 8
Abrupt changes, low-likelihood high impact events and critical thresholds, including tipping points, in the Earth system

Information for responses

Interactive Atlas

Chapter 10
Climate information and services

 Chapter 9
Earth system responses under pathways towards temperature stabilization, including overshoot pathways

Chapter 1
Framing, methods and knowledge sources

Chapter 5
Scenarios and projected future global temperatures

AR7 WGI - expected advances

Improved understanding of recent anomalies (outstanding regional or global extremes and values in global indices)

AR7 WGI - expected advances

Integration of advances on main processes and feedbacks at the interface of Earth system components and cycles (e.g., water-energy-carbon, ocean/land)

Chapter 4
Advances in process understanding of Earth system changes

Chapter 8
Abrupt changes, low-likelihood high impact events and critical thresholds, including tipping points, in the Earth system

Interactive Atlas

Chapter 3
Changes in regional climate and extremes, and their causes

Chapter 7
Projections of regional climate and extremes

Chapter 10
Climate information and services

Chapter 2
Large-scale changes in the climate system and their causes

Chapter 6
Global projections of Earth System responses across timescales

Chapter 9
Earth system responses under pathways towards temperature stabilization, including overshoot pathways

Chapter 1
Framing, methods and knowledge sources

Chapter 5
Scenarios and projected future global temperatures

AR7 WGI - expected advances

Global & regional projections based on new model developments (km scale resolution, AI, emulators), including extreme events

AR7 WGI - expected advances

Fast increasing literature on potential abrupt changes and events not covered by regional extremes

AR7 WGI - expected advances

Very dynamic areas of policy-relevant research
(climate services, stabilization and overshoot)

3. Project Results

3a. How can we track progress in the real world and anticipate risks?

Joeri Rogelj

Indicators of Global Climate Change

Key Indicators of Global Climate Change

Since IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

The intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports on climate system indicators every 5-10 years

Given how rapidly the climate system is changing and

Governments and policymakers need to make decisions informed by the latest science to avoid the worst impacts

This group of leading scientists from across the world come together to fill the “information gap” between the IPCC reports

Indicators of Global Climate Change 2024:

Annual update of key indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence

Forster et al. (2025)

Indicators of Global Climate Change

igcc earth 2025
Key Indicators of Global Climate Change:
Percentage change since IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (2021)

Multiple lines of evidence point to a **clear, consistent but worsening picture**

Human activities are changing the climate system **at a rate and scale not experienced since records began.**

Indicators of Global Climate Change

Indicators of Global Climate Change

Key Indicators of
Global Climate Change
Since IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

Total Greenhouse Gas Emissions

+1.3%

IPCC 6th assessment → IGCC assessment 2024

52.9
GtCO₂ e/year

53.6
GtCO₂ e/year

Key Indicators of
Global Climate Change
Since IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

Remaining Carbon Budget (± 1.5°C, 50% probability)

-74.0%

IPCC 6th assessment → IGCC assessment 2024

500
GtCO₂

130
GtCO₂

3b. How effectively will our mitigation actions result in a peak and decline in global warming?

Roland Séférian

Joeri Rogelj

Relationship between emission & warming

Use of the climate response to **cumulative emissions** has narrowed the range of the **remaining carbon budget**.

But its uncertainty is little changed from AR5 to AR6:

- AR5 *likely* range 0.8 – 2.5 °C per EgC
- **AR6 *likely* range 1.0 – 2.3 °C per EgC**

IPCC AR5, SPM.10

Research areas on the emission-warming relationship

Mitigation pathways holding global warming below 1.5 °C

Global total net CO₂ emissions
(GtC y⁻¹)

IPCC SR15 (2018)

Beyond the overall uncertainties of the emission-to-warming relationship, there are still many **areas of policy-relevant questions in conjunction with future emission pathways:**

- Earth system response to net zero (including timing)
- Earth system response to net negative emission (carbon dioxide removal)
- Characterization of climate overshoots
- Climate stabilization in general

Methodological advances thanks to emission-driven models

A new protocol with fixed CO₂ emission rate has been developed

← Fixed emission rate →
← Net-zero emissions →
← Net-negative emissions →

Sanderson et al. (2025)

This framework:

- Provides a more accurate way to calculate emission-warming metrics. (compared to the ad hoc methodology used in CMIP6/AR6)
- Enables consistent comparison between Earth system models and emulators.
- Establishes a relevant surrogate for (idealised) overshoot simulations.

Methodological advances thanks to emission-driven models

Assessing the climate response to cumulative emissions

CMIP6 – assessment in **concentration** mode

CMIP7 - assessment in **emission** mode

This framework
shines a light on:

- A **reduction** of the inter-model **spread**
- **Climate response** to cumulative emission is **revised downwards**

Methodological advances thanks to emission-driven models

Assessing the climate response to cumulative emissions

CMIP6 – assessment in **concentration** mode

CMIP7 - assessment in **emission** mode

→ Suggests a much **better consistency** between ESMs and emulators

How much warming is in the pipeline?

Palazzo Corner et al.
Frontiers in Science
(2023)

How much warming is in the pipeline?

Palazzo Corner et al.
Frontiers in Science (2023)

How much warming is in the pipeline? It depends.

Global mean temperature response to zero emissions

Global Mean Surface Air **Temperature** anomaly

The **higher the temperature** at which zero-emissions are achieved, the **larger the likelihood** that **global mean warming will continue** even thereafter.

How much warming is in the pipeline? It depends

Temperature change 50y after CO₂ emissions are reduced to net zero

Quantification of how much **warming or cooling** is expected **after net-zero CO₂ emissions.**

Reaching net-zero CO₂ at:

- 2.8-2.9°C → **1-in-2** chance of more warming
- 2.2-2.3°C → **1-in-3** chance of more warming
- 1.1-1.2°C → **1-in-10** chance of more warming

Palazzo Corner et al. (in review)

How much warming after net-zero CO₂ emissions?

We built a model to predict ZEC from observables

We can now track our expectation of **how much warming** is in the pipeline **based on observables** delivered on an annual basis:

- Surface air temperature (IGCC)
- Effective radiative forcing (IGCC)
- Change in ocean heat content (IGCC)
- Net atmosphere to land carbon flux (GCP)

Land-Based Carbon Dioxide Removal

Risks of under-delivery of land-based removal approaches quantified

Paris-compatible **scenarios** often **rely on** substantial amounts of **Carbon Dioxide Removal**, such as afforestation and/or biomass energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)

Using ESMs results to scale BECCS efficacy in existing IAM scenarios

Actual removals may be **less than half of those anticipated** by IAMs

Land-Based Carbon Dioxide Removal

Hedging against uncertainties in forest carbon pools

Forest-based mitigation effectiveness is sensitive to:

- Increasing forest disturbances
- Risk of overestimating the CO₂ fertilization
- Inefficient land-use conversions

Key findings

Accelerated decarbonization is key to meeting climate objectives despite forest carbon losses due to disturbances.

Delaying action on forest carbon loss **by five years doubles additional mitigation costs**, regardless of forest disturbance rates.

Summary of key messages

Tracking Global Warming

- **Groundbreaking efforts allow to track** our expectations of **how much warming** the world will experience under decreasing, net zero, and net negative emissions.

Effectiveness of Mitigation Actions

- **Earth System Modelling community is increasingly prepared** to answer questions directly related to the **effectiveness of carbon dioxide removal** in the context of overshoot.
- **Integrating insights from Earth system and socio-economic research communities** contributes to highlight risks to carbon dioxide removal strategies and their effectiveness.

3c. Does a stable global climate also imply stable regional climates?

Shuting Yang

Let's first have look at how some of the **processes that have a strong impact on large-scale climate** are expected to evolve under a warming, stable or cooling global climate...

Greenland ice sheet

Greenland ice sheet mass in simulation with:

- Ramp up (increasing emissions)
- Zero emissions (emissions peak)
- Ramp down (decreasing emissions/overshoot)

Key findings

- **Increasing emissions:** Greenland ice sheet melting accelerates with the warming level.
- **Zero emissions:** Melting continues in a zero-emission world.
- **Decreasing emissions (after overshoot):** Melting continues after overshoot when decrease starts from higher warming levels.

Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)

AMOC in simulation with:

- Ramp up (increasing emissions)
- Zero emissions (emissions peak)
- Ramp down (decreasing emissions/overshoot)

Key findings

- **Increasing emissions:** Strong AMOC reduction but no complete collapse with increasing emissions.
- **Zero emissions:** Some recovery; at higher warming levels less or no recovery.
- **Decreasing emissions (after overshoot):** Different behaviour across ESMs; overshoot over pre-industrial levels possible.

Atmospheric circulation response to zero emissions

Winter zonal **wind speed differences** in the first and last 100 years of a zero-emission simulation started from **different warming levels**

Key findings

Atmospheric circulation **continues to change** after reaching zero-emissions.

↳ this will likely affect weather patterns and extreme event occurrence

Further investigation is needed.

2°C
global
warming

4°C
global
warming

Low-cloud feedback

- 60-year long simulations at high-resolution (9km) of low clouds.
- Observed record-low planetary albedo in year 2023

Key findings

Low (and mid-level) cloud cover reduces by about 2.5% in the simulation

Expected future warming depends on how much of the **albedo decline** is due to **internal variability**, **reduced aerosol concentrations**, or **low-cloud feedback**.

A CERES Planetary Albedo Anomaly 2023

Goessling et al., 2024

CMIP7 — optional meltwater forcing

Increasing discharge from melting ice sheets is not accounted for in CMIP

- Increasing meltwater can delay surface warming and impact the ocean overturning. This is absent from models
- We suggest a forcing for CMIP7 to explore this effect ([Schmidt et al. 2025](#))
- May lead to more robust and coherent simulation of sea surface temperature, sea ice and regional sea level trends

Many of these processes are associated with the climate of key regions, but changes in their behavior **can have large-scale consequences.**

Let's now look at **abrupt changes and tipping points.**

Abrupt changes and state transitions

Key findings

- Polar regions most vulnerable: mainly regional sea ice collapses.
- Ocean circulation changes in North Atlantic
- Abrupt changes and transitions occur in some CMIP6 models below 1.5 K warming.

Impacts of potential tipping points (even after zero emissions)

Key findings

Consequences of an AMOC collapse for average precipitation in four climate models

Precipitation will decrease substantially in densely populated tropical monsoon regions.

Ben-Yami et al., 2024 Earth's Future

Quantifying tipping probabilities is not possible due to climate models' shortcomings.

New research focus

- Impose tipping in models and study impacts.
- Next year: Impact assessments at 25 km resolution

Recent observed trends in major tipping elements

Key findings

Some observational evidence suggests that the **stability of several key Earth system components has declined over the last century**, making tipping more likely.

This includes:

- The Greenland ice sheet
- The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
- The Amazon rainforest
- The South American monsoon.

And what about the stability of regional climate?

European temperature response to zero emissions

Key findings

- **During increasing emissions:** Regional warming larger than global mean but differs between ESMs despite similar global mean warming.
- **Zero emissions:** No clear temperature change signal under zero emissions.
- **During decreasing emissions (after overshoot):** European temperature falls below pre-industrial temp. level.

The European climate will not be stable after reaching zero emissions

S. Wang

Global climate change impact at the regional scale

Global climate change impact varies at the regional scale → e.g. across different European cities

decreasing ↓

Urban Heat Island
effect (UHI)

↑ increasing

Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia
et al., in prep.

Key findings

- Climate change typically leads to warming in **cities** and their **rural surroundings**.
- Most cities, like **Brussels**, may show weaker temp. differences to their surroundings in the future.
- There are other examples, like **Milan**, where the heat island effect may increase.
- Causes for this contrasting behaviour are being investigated and the specific urban factors that determine how city climate will evolve in the future.

Summary of key messages

1

Climate processes relevant for regional climates, such as land ice melting, ocean circulation and heat uptake, **will continue to change**, and **tipping points could still be crossed** even after reaching zero emissions.

3

Changes will **affect weather patterns which will likely impact extremes**, but more research is needed to explore how extremes may change.

2

Regional climates will **continue to change** under stable global temperatures. Generally, oceans will continue to warm and land areas will tend to cool, but regional differences are expected to be large.

4

Cities and rural regions will show pronounced differences in their response to climate change.

ClimTip About Objectives Newsroom Webinars Publications Funded by the European Union

Quantifying climate tipping points *and their impacts*

Safeguarding Earth systems stability by understanding and addressing climate tipping points

Read Our Key Messages

Latest science *and news* [Visit Newsroom](#)

WEBINAR AMOC Collapse WHAT HAPPENS IF IT TIPS? And why can't we predict when...

Events ClimTip & TipESM Joint Conference and Annual Meetings

WEBINAR AMOC Tipping Point OBSERVATIONS VS. MODELS Are We Closer Than We Think?

Webinars Reconciled Warning Signals Suggest a Nearing AMOC Tipping Point

For 12 specific “key messages” on tipping points, see <https://www.climate-tipping-points.eu/key-messages>

4. Outstanding knowledge gaps and research needs

Roland Séférian

Outstanding knowledge gaps

How do we design climate strategies that deliver effective adaptation and mitigation despite diverse and persistent Earth system uncertainties?

How do we bridge from state-of-the-art ESM research to policy-relevant information?

- Improved coordination across research communities (e.g. ESM, IAM, Impact modelling) and during CMIP/AR cycles would ease implementation and save resources.
- Improved interfacing between IAMs and ESMs, including integrating ESM insights and uncertainties in identification of IAM mitigation strategies that are robust.
- Dedicated efforts in tools for quantitative science synthesis and translation.

What are approaches and limits to managing our Earth system under overshoot?

- Earth System response to increasing and decreasing emissions
- Effectiveness and reliability of CDR in a changing climate
- Need for intertemporal governance structures for Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR)

Outstanding knowledge gaps

What explains the recent record-warm years? (role of clouds, aerosols, and internal variability?)

Improving knowledge on tipping points

- Need for likelihood assessment of tipping points occurring at different warming levels.
- Assessment of tipping point impacts on sectors such as:
 - Human Health (heat stress, infectious diseases)
 - Ecosystems (biomes, fire)
 - Food systems (crop indices)
 - Water (hydrological drought and flooding)
 - Infrastructure and Energy (hydro power)
 - Marine and Coastal (ports, marine heat waves)

5. Lessons learned from EU project implementation

Mariana Rocha

Lessons learned from EU project implementation

Stakeholder engagement

- Enhancing stakeholder engagement is important to ensure models serve societal needs effectively.
- Co-design is crucial to improve stakeholder engagement and policy initiatives.

Climate Education

EU projects are particularly well-placed to push forward education initiatives that promote:

- High-level teacher capacity building on climate science.
- Exchanges between European schools and teachers.

Lessons learned from EU project implementation

Cross-project collaboration

- Fosters knowledge exchange for better and more-aligned research outputs.
- Improves D/E/C efforts and Impact of individual projects by:
 - (i) increasing reach/relevance of individual project's initiatives.
 - (ii) reducing stakeholder/policy fatigue.

Climate knowledge professionals

Fostering exchanges between climate knowledge professionals in different projects is an efficient leverage:

- to improve cross-project collaboration on D/E/C initiatives.
- to promote capacity building of the staff in charge of D/E/C in EU projects.

Links to Relevant Resources

Links to Relevant Resources

[Exploring methane emissions and mitigation strategies through Earth System Models - ESM2025](#)

[From Earth System Models to Integrated Assessment Models: Bridging the gap in climate modelling - ESM2025](#)

[Policy Brief: New scenarios shed light on the role of carbon dioxide removal - RESCUE](#)

[Policy Brief 2025: Strengthening climate science and modelling communities through hackathons - nextGEMS](#)

[Raising Awareness of Earth System Tipping Points: Implications for EU Governance – TipESM](#)

[Global Tipping Points Report 2023 - OptimESM](#)

[ClimTip – Understanding and Assessing Climate Tipping Points](#)
(incl. research communities' key messages about tipping points)